

Emotion Management through Workplace Design

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Abstract

The quest to design work environments conducive to the needs of their inhabitants has long been the central challenge for architects and designers. Still, existing workplace research offers limited guidance to the question of *how can workplace design enable organizations and people in coping with emotions of uncertainty and fear that accompany change*, an emerging dilemma of critical importance to the business and architectural communities.

In an era where managing change becomes central to the managerial conduct, when the failure rate of companies' change initiatives is now identified to exceed 70 percent, and where the 'recipients of change' are emotionally distressed and cognitively disoriented understanding how to facilitate emotion management during times of change becomes key to individual well being and organizational success.

Among the prime reasons for the dismal change management results is organizational members' resistance and difficulty in confronting uncertainties. Many develop symptoms of anxiety, fear, aggression, confusion, and frustration manifested in over-employment of defense mechanisms like repression, regression, reaction formation and denial. What often results from the emotionally-threatening change experience is a cocooning behavior where people withdraw to protect their emotional self.

Our work is centered on the presupposition that the affect of designed workplace environments on organization and individual change management is understudied and perhaps under-exploited. We integrate several perspectives including change and adaptation, architectural design, and industrial psychology to frame the workplace design - emotion link and discuss possible ways by which workplace design can enable organizational and individual management of emotions conducive to change.

Keywords: Workplace design, emotion management, change

On workplace design & organizational change

Many of the workplace design accounts treat change as a non-problematic contextual factor briefly discussing ways in which the work has changed over the past decades due to forces of globalization, the introduction of new technologies, and the overall increase in competition across industries (n1). These accounts proceed to suggest that workplace design solutions must address these changes in contextual conditions to support organizational needs to regain and sustain competitiveness through flat, responsive, collaborative structures. What follows is

a discussion of workplace design possibilities that can best mirror the organizational structure/restructure requirements and enable their implementation (Figure 1)

Figure 1, Current view of the role of workplace design in supporting organizational response to change

For example, the solution of open space as a design lever attempting to enable emergent interactions and teamwork as means to enhance organizational cross-boundary collaborations for new knowledge development (Bencivengn 1998; Stone and Luchetti 1985). Implicit to this approach is the notion that design for collaboration will most likely lead to greater capacity of idea generation which in turn will support the organization’s pursuit of innovation (n2). It is necessary to note however that these assumptions, although intuitively appealing, enjoy only limited empirical support.

While workplace design decisions are derived at times from organizational restructuring needs to enable better adaptation to change (Vischer, 1995), rarely do these design decisions address the complexity of the *change phenomenon itself* (Gulasch, 1998) and its affect on organization members that need to make sense of the change and manage themselves and others through this experience effectively. For example, the continuous abandonment of hierarchical structures (Galbraith, 1995; Ancona et al. 1998) exposes employees to increased levels of uncertainty (Chan, 2000) but the discussion of workplace solutions seems to ignore the impact of uncertainty that this change brings to people’s *emotional* and *cognitive* states.

It is of little surprise that many transformation efforts fail to achieve their desired ends (Kotter, 1995). Research suggests that the failure rate of organizational change attempts is as high as 70 percent (Beer and Mitra, 2000). Among the prime reasons for these dismal results is employees’ resistance to ‘own’ the change and bear the associated emotional and cognitive

burden (Skoldberg, 1994; Huy, 1999; Dirks et al, 1996). Instead, many develop symptoms of anxiety, fear, aggression, confusion, and frustration (Marks, 1991; Marks and Mirvis, 1985; Marris, 1986; Diamond, 1993; Hirschhorn and Gilmore, 1989) manifested in resistance (Kotler and Schlesinger, 1979) and over-employment of defense mechanisms including repression, regression, reaction formation and denial (Oldham and Kleiner, 1990). What often results from the emotional threatening and cognitively challenging change experience is a cocooning - learned helplessness behavior (Antonacopoulou and Gabriel, 2001; Seligman, 1974) where people are withdrawing to protect their emotional self and appear to display rigidity (n3).

And so, while the workplace literature discusses solutions to support strategic intents of organizations (e.g. increased responsiveness and cross boundary collaboration to support customer focus and innovation development), the view of the *individual*, on whom the implementation of strategic and structural adaptation depends, remains limited to task related issues at best, while state of mind and heart are largely overlooked (Figure 2).

Figure 2, Can workplace design enable both organizational and individual change management

The current voice of the workplace literature is primarily occupied with designing work environments that allow flexible and effective adaptation of *organizations* to their environments. For example, as collaboration within and across disciplines becomes key to the successful management of new knowledge development, workplace researchers embrace open spaces and communal solutions (Lohr, 1997; Kupritz, 1998; Ferguson, 2001; Duffy,

1997; Asirvatham, 1999; Milford, 1997) as design vehicles that enable collaboration, emergent interactions and serendipitous communication to take place among people (Becker and Steele, 1995) in the pursuit of new knowledge development (Cantrell, 2001; Cohen, 1999; Loftness, 2001; Pollack, 2001; Degenhardt, 2001). These open spaces are often furnished with mobile team office furniture that allows flexible configuration of continuous roundtable interactions (Veitch and Gifford, 1996; Wheeler, 2001; Cruikshank and Malcolm, 1994). *While these design considerations are clearly important, they solely address the organization's task-set while neglecting to attend to the well being of individuals reacting to and coping (n4) with the change* (Vince and Bourssine, 1996).

Figure 3, Current focus of workplace design research literature

Clearly, the emotional undercurrents of change have profound consequences to individual behavior within organizations. Psychoanalysts insist that there is a universally primitive, pre-social, pre-linguistic, and pre-cognitive level of emotions which might be experienced or repressed, expressed or controlled, dominant or diffused, but never ignored and obliterated (Gabriel, 1998; Craib, 1998; Hopfl and Linstead, 1997). Still Fineman (1993) has already alerted us that organizations by large often fail to nourish people's psyche and ignore their emotional needs. Moreover, organizations undergoing transformation often try to espouse positive pro-change rhetoric, evoking emotional dissonance in individuals that need to reconcile their naturally arising negative emotions of fear and anxiety with the organization's change hype (Middleton, 1989).

The literatures on change and adaptation (n5) (Walsh, 1995; Chan, 2000; Dirks et al., 1996) both address the criticality of managing emotions throughout change efforts as change events are considered threatening stressors that are often perceived negatively by organizational members (Mossholder et al., 2000; O'Neill and Lenn, 1995; Kets de Vries and Miller, 1985;

Oldham and Kleiner, 1990). The reality of change therefore is *emotionally* charged and is challenging both to organizations and their individual members, a challenge that threatens to undermine the effectiveness of the organizational change effort altogether (Armenakis et al., 1993).

Figure 4, Potential impact of workplace design as an enabler of simultaneous organizational and individual change

Thus workplace design might be one of very few existing levers capable of sustaining both organizational problem solving and individual emotional coping efforts, marrying what Metzger (1963) has termed ‘Reality1’, the reality that is manifested through artifact design, and ‘Reality2’, the one that is experienced and acted upon. *But what specifically be the role that workplace design can play in enabling individuals and organizations to manage change?*

Managing emotions through workplace design

Our discussion that views the physical design of the workplace as enabling the management of a wide variety of individuals’ emotions builds off contemporary thinking in the field of design that views designing as a possibility-creating activity focused on the *relationship* between the user and the design (be it designed products, objects or environments) and creates a context for *experience* (Hekkert, 2001). According to this view design should shift from creating products to creating *contexts for experience* where the user is seduced to experience the designed object or reality with all senses (Overbeeke et al., 1999). By

designing contexts for experience instead of simply products, objects and/or environments the focus shifts from the result *of* interaction towards the involvement *during* interaction (Hummels, 1999). This person-design interactive experience is affective in nature and involves a great variety of emotions, moods, and feelings.

Along these lines, Desmet & Hekkert (2001) argued that of all affective states or experiences, the emotional experience is the most relevant for understanding product experience because only *emotions* imply a one-to-one relationship between the experience and the object. If a design looks or performs in a way that corresponds with a concern of the individual, a pleasant emotional response will result and conversely, if it conflicts, the emotion will be unpleasant. Designs evoke emotions when they're perceived to touch upon individuals' concerns or preference (Frijda, 1986; Reeves & Nass, 1996).

Yet, before we proceed we must note that the term 'emotion' is still regarded problematic inasmuch that it enjoys multiple conceptualizations and little consensus regarding definitions (n6). In general, the literature on the subject of emotions is divided into two broad schools, highly heterogeneous in themselves, that debate whether to conceptualize emotions as anchored in dimensions (Wundt, 1924; Masson & McCarthy, 1995; Watson, 2000; Damasio, 1999; Johnston and Scherer, 2000; Cosmides and Tooby, 2000) or discrete categories (Lazarus, 1991; Plutchik, 1962, 2001). However, despite this divergence, Plutchik is rightfully pointing to some emergent consensus regarding the notions that *emotions are usually triggered by one's interpretations of events, that they involve strong reactions of many bodily systems, that they communicate information from one person to another, and that they help the individual adapt to changing environmental situations* (Plutchik, 2003).

As design creates a context for experience that is experienced emotionally by persons through interacting with that design, the emotions evoked convey meaning and enable or hinder adaptation to change. Echoing this line of thought, Fredrickson (2000) develops an insightful argument pointing to the significant role of positive emotions (specified in Fredrickson's research as joy, contentment and interest) in broadening a person's thought-action repertoire and building that individual's enduring personal resources, resources that also served the ancestral function of promoting survival. Fredrickson provides a detailed account on the relationship that exists between negative emotions and the narrowing of one's thought process and action repertoire and conversely the affect that positive emotions have on one's

ability to generate creative thought, relationship with others and overall higher levels of performance and survivability. Moreover, Fredrickson proposes that positive emotions have an undoing effect on negative emotions.

Supporting Fredrickson, Norman (2002) argues that positive affect enhances creative, breadth-first thinking whereas negative affect focuses cognition, enhancing depth-first processing and minimizing distractions. Therefore, Norman continues, it is essential that products/objects designed for use under stress follow good human-centered design, for stress makes people less able to cope with difficulties and less flexible in their approach to problem solving, while positive affect makes people more tolerant of minor difficulties and more flexible and creative in finding solutions. Thus, Norman concludes just as negative affect can make some simple tasks difficult, positive affect can make some difficult tasks easier, and both affects can be triggered and/or facilitated by design.

To further support this point, Isen (1993) showed that the positive affective system seems to change the cognitive parameters of problem solving to emphasize breadth-first thinking, and the examination of multiple solutions and courses of action. Conversely, anxiety has just the opposite effect: it biases the processing to be depth first, focused, concentrated and overall it narrows the thought process. In general, negative affect enables one to focus upon a specific threat or problem, but is likely to prevent adaptive and creative problem solving that is usually required under conditions of change and uncertainty (Mills and Kleinman, 1988).

As we begin to tie this discussion of emotions to ideas about the design of workplace environments, we become interested in workplace designs that can create a context for experiencing positive emotions that can override negative emotions of fear, anxiety and anger that often accompany change, and broaden rather than limit individuals' creative and adaptive thought-action repertoire.

What is the role that emotion should play in our approaches to design?
“How do we design for emotion?” Good question, but it implies that one can identify emotion as a design target, then craft an artifact (an application, a device, a thing, for example) that meets this target (Don Norman, Symposium on Foundations of Interaction Design, 2003).

And so, if emotions can be influenced by the deliberate designing of contexts for experience (n7), what particular levers can designers employ to carefully architecture a desired experience? While contemporary literature on workplace design often elaborates on communal and team spaces as design enablers of communication, Mahnke (1996) takes a different route discussing in great detail the affect of *color* and light in designed environments on the emotional well being of their inhabitants. Mahnke presents his and others' color-emotion association studies (n8) and points to significant relationship between specific colors and specific emotions. For example, his summarizing discussion of the color Gray suggests that:

Pure Gray is conservative, quiet, and calm, but also dreary, tedious, passive and without life...in the Gray zone there is no clarity in any direction – it is neutral...Gray lacks energy; it has no will of its own. It does not want to get involved and make any definite statement. In color design it takes on the characteristic of the adjacent color (p.66)

Yellow however enjoys a very different set of characteristics:

Reflective and luminous, Yellow is the happiest of all colors. In its positive associations and impressions it is cheerful, high-spirited, and suggestive of the life-giving sun. It represents a bright future, hope, wisdom and it is expansive -not earthbound... Yellow is used in packaging and advertising to express activity and cheerfulness.

While Yellow is associated with happiness, Gray is correlated with mourning and sorrow across a number of studies. Why is it then that the interior of offices in the corporate world is so heavily decorated with Gray? What affective experience is created by totally 'Gray-ing' cubical walls and office furniture? (n9) Research shows that persons subjected to understimulations showed symptoms of restlessness, excessive emotional response, difficulty in concentration, irritation and in some cases, a variety of more extreme reactions (Mahnke and Mahnke, 1993, P5). At the same time, totally 'de-Gray-ing' the workplace environment may not be the solution either. Kuller collected measurements during the 1st, 2nd and 3rd hours of exposure to multi-color environment and found that subjects generally experienced a lack of emotional control in the colorful room. Subjects EKG (heart rate) was slower in the colorful room than in the Gray one, which is in agreement with a hypothesis of other

researchers (Lacey et al, 1963) that intense attention might be accompanied by cardiac deceleration. Mahnke and Mahnke write:

It is especially interesting to note that brain-wave activity was lower in the colorful room than in the gray room and the heart response was slower in the colorful room. Therefore, we may conclude that a dull environment tends to prod brain activity, which may induce anxiety, fear and distress (1993, p.6)

Thus, studies have demonstrated that coloring and visual patterning of the interior space might have a profound physiological and psychological effect on inhabitants' emotional experience of that space. From a design standpoint the question of unity versus complexity of color selection as well as other design elements and stimuli becomes crucial in designing contexts for desired affective experience (Ellinger 1963).

Although the affective experience of designed environment, one that is shaped by color as well as by additional design considerations, is profound and has a significant impact on people's performance at work, this topic is still understudied and largely ignored by management. As suggested earlier, this knowledge could be particularly useful in times where organizations and their citizens are confronted with increasing levels of change and uncertainty and need to attend to negative emotions while at the same time creatively construct sense and direction. Designing workplace environments, as contexts for affective experience can be leveraged as a carefully architected lever to assist in eliciting positive emotions while better containing negative ones.

Contemporary workplace design cases and future direction

There is evidence from a small but growing number of companies that the design of the physical workplace can have a significant affect on the emotional well being of organization members as well as the culture of the organization at large during times of change. Chief executives from companies including Alcoa, SEI Investments, Muzak, Allsteel, Tribune Interactive and Green Mountain Power have used the design of the workplace to enable or change their corporate culture. The office can have a major impact on the experience and effectiveness of work. Among other things, these executives wanted the employees to feel

that they all are an equally important part of the organization; to be more collaborative; to be more innovative; and for work to be fun as we will discuss shortly.

Understanding the power of the design of the workplace is not new. Robert Propst in his classic book *The Office: A Facility Based on Change* (1968), illustrated that the idea in using systems furniture was an office space that was open with some enclosure of a partition to include storage. The book includes illustrations of an enclosed cubicle as “bad.” Tom Allen of MIT in his book, *Managing the Flow of Technology* (1997) included a chapter “The influence of architecture on communication.” Major findings from Allen’s research demonstrated that physical barriers between people, including walls, dramatically reduced successful communication. People on different floors were even less likely to communicate. More recently, a number of researchers and authors have found evidence for the importance of the physical place. John Seely Brown and Paul Duguid, in their book *The Social Life of Information*, pointed out that “good office design can produce powerful learning environments...people often find what they need to know by virtue of where they sit and who they see.”

Our discussion focuses on sharing a series of company examples and the views of the chief executives of these companies:

I. As part of the seven year process of reinvention at Alcoa, Paul O’Neill, CEO, felt that a new headquarters office was essential to that process: “There’s an unbelievable difference that’s unleashed in human potential with the right physical surroundings.” In 1998 Alcoa moved into its new headquarters, a 6-story building with a large atrium and open escalators to promote interaction, leaving a 31-story tower. Everyone, including the CEO was in the same size open office cubicle. According to O’Neill the building was “fabulously successful”.

II. In changing the culture of SEI Investments, now located in Oaks, PA, outside of Philadelphia, the last thing Chairman and CEO Al West wanted to do was spend money on the office because he felt it was an unnecessary perk. At the end of the reinvention process, after moving into a new headquarters, West now feels that the workplace is one of the major reasons for the success of the company. The objective was to enable people to work effectively and collaboratively in teams. The unexpected result was that the physical environment became a sales piece for a company that demonstrated that they were different.

One division of the organization achieved a 90% close rate if they brought potential clients to the new headquarters.

III. The reinvention of Muzak is a well understood opportunity given the universal brand recognition of the company that brought us “elevator music”. Muzak also had the world’s largest digital music library of songs by original artists and was shifting in focus to become “audio architects,” providing customized music for thousands of companies. To Bill Boyd, CEO, the new building “would help us remember everyday what we are, and for everyone who walked in here, every customer, every franchisee, it would reinforce our new brand and our new promise.” Did the reinvention work? 2002, not a good year for most companies, was the best year Muzak ever had. In the five years since reinvention they have more than doubled their revenue.

IV. Not all new offices are new construction. Tribune Interactive reused a three story space that had been empty for twenty years in the center of Chicago, converting it into 12,000 sq. feet of office space. As “fostered collaboration improved teamwork and encouraged creativity.” Allsteel too reused a factory for a new headquarters.

More detailed case study research needs to be done on these and other companies. Evidence already gathered demonstrates the power of the workplace to effect change towards achieving innovation. New research approaches in Europe and the US are beginning to provide more detailed evidence of the benefit of workplace design. What predictions then can we make for a future that has already begun? What direction should workplace design take to better meet the needs of organizations and their inhabitants in the years to come? Following is a preliminary set of assumptions and predictions that guide our conceptual and actionable knowledge development:

1. The world of work will continue to be unpredictable, with varying rates of change and increased uncertainty. It will be more difficult to extrapolate future needs from past experience, and therefore difficult to create structures (social and physical) that can be instituted and then left on their own for long periods. This suggests a compelling need for organizations to be agile and adaptable, with the ability to re-structure parts or the whole without big time delays (which would render the changes useless). Leaders will

need to be asking "what structures are needed?" in a much more continuous way than is typical today.

2. Workplaces will need to provide a relatively "loose- fit design" not tied to particular social structures or groupings in order to be usable. Re-structuring quickly will be key to remaining competitive and the workplace has to support this requirement.
3. Adaptability will also require/allow more mobility, with a looser definition of "workplace." People will continue to experiment with breaking old conventions about where and when work is done, and expectations about work styles will focus more on results and less on "looking good/right" while achieving them.
4. Technology advances will continue to support greater mobility, especially wireless systems that free people from specific work locations and allow them to choose spots for other reasons than wiring or outlets. New materials and configurations of work furniture are also helping people to re-configure their workplaces in a short time with little or not cost.
5. Companies will tend to emphasize re-use of resources and physical spaces; infra-structures and materials will need to be robust and hold up to such re-use. Designs will have to allow for rearrangements without getting into expensive changes in walls and wiring. Another possibility is further development of enclosure systems that can flex to provide different balances between individual privacy and collective contact and collaboration. Consequently, there will likely be fewer big projects to create new places from scratch, and more continuous adaptations and upgrading to get more flexibility.
6. There will also need to be a greater awareness of social factors (policies, norms and culture) that affect the full and best use of the potential of workplaces. Effectiveness will be improved by changes in patterns of use rather than just in physical settings per se. A work environment will be treated as a total system of physical, technical and social components, and changes will likely be made on all three fronts whenever new work patterns are needed or new problems are solved.
7. Finally workplace design will become more sophisticatedly oriented towards facilitating emotions and behaviors required to adapt and innovate. Greater emphasis will be placed on managing the tension of unity-complexity (e.g. individual-team /open-close spaces, color palettes) to build contexts for particular affective experience of individuals and groups.

NOTES

1- For example, “Uncertainty is endemic and chronic in today’s organizations. The reasons reveal themselves in daily newspaper and TV headlines: mammoth mergers and acquisitions, technology that changes with anxiety-provoking speed, a labor force for which demand greatly exceeds supply for qualified workers, fierce and unpredictable global markets and competition, and new products and services lead by e-commerce that rewrite the rules of the game with dizzying speed. All of these factors force organizations to rethink how they do business: how they manage their business, where and when they convene workers, and the manner in which work is done” (Becker and Sims, 2000:5)

2- See Nonaka and Konno’s discussion of the concept of ‘Ba’ (1998), a shared space for emerging relationships, where knowledge conversations can take place and consequently new knowledge can be created.

3- Threat-rigidity thesis is based on research showing that when faced with threatening conditions, change included, individuals regress to behave in a rigid way, relying on well known behaviors or dominant responses, restricting their behaviors and shutting their emotions down (Ocasio, 1995; Staw et al. 1981)

4- Here, coping with change is defined as the exertion of behavioral and cognitive efforts to manage the internal and external demands of relationship with the environment that tax or surpass the person’s resources (Folkman et al, 1986).

5- These fairly elaborated literatures can be found within various psychoanalytic and social psychology schools but rarely has their voice echoed in the business change management literature.

6- William James, 1884: “My theory is that the body changes follow directly the perception of the exciting fact, and that our feelings of the same change as they occur is the emotion” (p.204)

Sigmund Freud, 1915: Ideas are cathexes – ultimately of memory traces – while affects and emotions correspond with process of discharge, the final expression of which is perceived as feeling.

Robert Plutchik, 1962: Emotion is the felt tendency towards anything intuitively appraised as good (beneficial) or away from anything intuitively appraised as bad (harmful). This attraction or aversion is accompanied by a pattern of physiological change, organized towards approach or withdrawal. The pattern differs for different emotions.

Nico Frijda, 1986: Emotions are tendencies to establish, maintain, or disrupt a relationship with the environment... Emotion might be defined as action readiness change in response to emergencies or interruptions...

J. Campos, D.L. Mumme, R. Kermoian, and R.G. Campos, 1994: Emotions are processes that establish, maintain, change, or terminate the relationship between the person and the environment on matters of significance to a person

Leda Cosmides and John Tooby, 2000: An emotion is a superordinate program whose function is to direct the activities and interactions of the subprograms governing perception; attention; interfaces; learning; memory; goal choice; motivational priorities; and physiological reactions, etc.

7- The internationally respected architect, Sven Hesselgren coined the term 'emotional loading' to characterize an element of architectural design inherent in any interior or exterior environment. (In Mahnke, 1996, p.47)

8- See for example the work of Hupka et al, 1997 and Terwogt & Hoeksma, 1999

9- In the early days of the personal computer, all the display screens were black and white (...packaged in a gray plastic box – author's addition). When color screens were first introduced, I did not understand their popularity. In those days, color was primarily used either to highlight text or to add superfluous screen decoration. From a cognitive point of view, color added no value that could not be provided with the appropriate use of shading. But despite the fact that the interface community could find no scientific benefit, businesses insisted on buying color monitors. Obviously, color was fulfilling some need, but one we could not measure. In order to understand this phenomenon, I borrowed a color display to use with my computer. After the allocated time, I was convinced that my assessment had been correct -- color added no discernible value for everyday work. However, I refused to give up the color display. Although my reasoning told me that color was unimportant, my emotional reaction told me otherwise (Norman, 2002)

REFERENCES

- Allen, T. J. 1997. *Managing the Flow of Technology: Technology transfer and the dissemination of technological information within the research and development organization*. MIT Press
- Ancona, D., Kochan, T., Scully, M., van Maanen, J., & Westney, E. D. 1998. *Managing For the Future: Organizational Behavior and Processes*. South-West College Publishing: Florence, KY.
- Antonacopoulou, E. P. and Gabriel, Y. 2001. Emotion, learning, and organizational change: towards an integration of psychoanalytic and other perspectives. *Journal of organization change management*, Vol. 14(5): 435-451
- Armenakis, A. A., Harris, S. G. and Mossholder, K. W. 1993. Creating readiness for organizational change. *Human relations*, Vol. 46: 681-703
- Asirvatham, S. 1999. No More Cubes. *Journal of Property Management (July-August)*: 28-31.
- Becker, F. and Steele, F. 1995. *Workplace by Design: Mapping the High-Performance Workscape*. San Francisco: Jossey-Bass
- Beer, M. and Mitra, N. 2000. Cracking the code of change. *Harvard Business Review*, May/June
- Bencivenga, D. 1998. A Humanistic Approach to Space. *HRMagazine*. (March): 68- 78
- Brown, S. J and Duguid, P. 2000. *The Social Life of Information*. Harvard Business School Press.
- Cantrell, S. 2001. Choices in Workplace Design for High-End Knowledge Work. <http://www.smarttech.com/facilitydesign/feature.asp>
- Chan, D. 2000. Understanding adaptation to change in the work environment: integrating individual differences and learning perspectives. In Ferris GR (Ed), *Research in personnel and human resources management*. Vol .18: 1-42
- Cosmides, L. and Tooby, J. 2000, Evolutionary psychology and the emotions. In M.lewis& J.M.Haviland-Jones (Eds.), *handbook of Emotions* (pp. 91-115). New York: Guilford press
- Cruikshank, J. and Malcolm, C. 1994. *Herman Miller, Inc.: Buildings and Beliefs*. Washington, DC: The American Institute of Architects Press
- Craib, I. 1998. *Experiencing identity*. Sage: CA
- Cohen, D. 1999. Face to Face with Peter Lawrence. *Knowledge Connections: Newsletter of the Institute for Knowledge Management (April)*: 7-11.

- Damasio, A. 1999. *The Feeling of What Happens: Body and Emotion in the Making of Consciousness*. New York: Harcourt Brace
- Degenhardt, B. 2001. A New Design Approach. The Impact of Communication and Computing Technologies on the Office Environment in 2020. ASID Future Work 2020
- Desmet, P.M.A. & Hekkert, P. 2001. *The basis of product emotions*. In: P. Jordan and W.S.
- Dirks, K. T., Cummings, L. L. and Pierce, J. L. 1996. Psychological ownership in organizations: conditions under which individuals promote and resist change. *Research in organizational change and development*, Vol. 9: 1-23
- Diamond, M. 1993. *The unconscious life of organizations; interpretive organizational identity*. Quorum books: London
- Duffy, F. 1997. *The New Office: With 20 International Case Studies*, Conran Octopus Ltd: London
- Ellinger, R. G. 1963. *Color Structure and Design*. NY: Van Nostrand Reinhold
- Ferguson, B. 2001. Workplace Roles and Trends; Selected Perspective from Inside a Client Organization. ASID Future Work 2020; phase two
- Fineman, S. 1993. *Emotion in organizations*. Sage: CA
- Fredrickson, B. 2000. *Cultivating Positive Emotions to Optimize Health and Well-Being. Prevention & Treatment*, Vol. 3
- Frijda, N.H. 1986. *The Emotions*, Cambridge University Press, Cambridge, England.
- Gabriel, Y. 1998. Psychoanalytic contribution for the study of the emotional life of organizations. *Administrative and society*, Vol. 30(3): 291-314
- Galbraith, J. 1995. *Designing Organizations: An Executive Briefing on Strategy, Structure, and Process*. San Francisco. Jossey-Bass.
- Gulasch, M. 1998. *King the New Workplace Work - Ten Steps to Create Productive Workplaces for the Future*.
- Hall, T. "And the Walls Came Tumbling Down". *The New York Times Magazine*, 13 December 1998; 82-9.
- Hekkert, P. 2001. The experience of Design. Paper presented at the 4EAD conference, Aveiro, Portugal
- Hirschhorn, L. and Gilmore, T. 1989. The psychodynamics of a cultural change: learning from a factory. *Human resource management*, Vol. 28(2): 211-233
- Hopfl, H. and Linstead, S. 1997. Learning to feel and feeling to learn: emotion and learning in organizations. *Management learning*, Vol. 28(1): 5-12

- Hummels, C. 1999. Engaging Contexts to Evoke Experiences. In C.J. Overbeeke and P. Hekkert (Eds.). Proceedings of the international conference Design and Emotion 3-5 November 1999, Delft, The Netherlands, pp. 39-45.
- Huy, Q. N. 1999. Emotional capability, emotional intelligence, and radical change. *Academy of management review*, Vol. 24(2): 325-345
- Isen, A.M. 1993. Positive affect and decision-making. In M. Lewis & J. M. Haviland (Eds.), *Handbook of emotions* (pp. 261-277). New York: Guilford.
- Jick, T. 1996. A note on the recipients of change. Harvard business publishers case, 1- 11
- Johnston, T. and Scherer, K.R. 2000, Vocal Communications of emotion. In M. Lewis & J.M. Haviland-Jones (Eds.), *Handbook of emotions* (pp. 220-235). New York: Guilford Press
- Kets de Vries, M. F. R. and Miller, D. 1985. *The neurotic organization*. Jossey-Bass, SF
- Kotter, J. and Schlesinger, L. 1979. Choosing strategies for change. *Harvard business review*, March-April: 106-114
- Kotter, J. 1995. Leading Change: Why Transformation Efforts Fail. *Harvard business review*, March-April: 59-67
- Kupritz, V. 1998. Privacy in the Workplace: The Impact of Building Design. *Journal of Environmental Psychology* 18, 341-356
- Lacey, Kagan, Lacey and Moss. 1963. In Kuller, R. *The Use of Space - Some Physiological and Philosophical Aspects*. Paper presented at the Third International Architectural Psychology Conference, Universite Louis Pasteur, Strasbourg, France June 1976
- Lazarus, R. S. 1991. *Emotion and adaptation*. New York: Oxford University Press.
- Loftness, V. 2001. Adding Value: Productivity and Quality of Life in Futurework Environments. ASID Future Work 2020; phase two
- Lohr, S. 1997. Hey, Who Took the Office Doors? Rethinking Privacy vs. Teamwork in Today's Workplace. *New York Times* (11 August): 1-7.
- Mahnke, F. 1996. *Color, environment and human response*. Wiley: New York
- Mahnke, R. & Mahnke, F. 1993. *Color and Light* 1993, John Wiley & Sons
- Marks, M. 1991. Combating merger shock before the deal is closed. *Mergers and Acquisitions*, Vol. 25(4): 42-48
- Marks, M. and Mirvis, P. 1985. Merger syndrome: stress and uncertainty. *Mergers and Acquisitions*, Vol. 20(2): 50-55
- Marris, P. *Loss and change*. Rutledge: London

- Masson, J. & McCarthy, S. 1995, *When Elephants Weep*, New York, Dell Press
- Metzger, W. 1963. .Reality: what does it mean? *Psychological Reports*, Vol. 25: 127- 135.
- Milford, M. 1997. Dupont Shuts the Door on Private Offices. *New York Times* (23 February): 38.
- Mills, T., Kleinman, S., 1988, Emotions, Reflexivity, and Action: An Interactionist Analysis. *Social Forces*, Vol.66 No.4, (Chapel Hill: University of North Carolina Press, pp. 1009-1027.
- Mossholder, K. W., Settoon, R. P., Armenakis, A. A & Harris, S. G. 2000. Emotion during organizational transformations. *Group and organization management*, Vol. 25(3): 220-243
- Norman, D. A. 2002. Emotion and design: Attractive things work better. *Interactions Magazine*, ix (4), 36-42.
- Norman, D. A. 2003 Symposium on Foundations of Interaction Design.
http://hub.interaction-ivrea.it/blog/2003/11/emotion_cognition_and_design#002160
- O.Neil, H. M. and Lenn, D. J. 1995. Voices of survivors: words that downsizing CEOs should hear. *Academy of management executive*, Vol. 9(4): 23-34
- Oldham, M. and Kleiner, B. H. 1990. Understanding the nature and the use of defense mechanisms in organizational life. *Journal of managerial psychology*. Vol. 5(5): i-iv
- Overbeeke, C.J., Djajadiningrat, J.P., Wensveen, S.A.G., Hummels, C.C.M. 1999. Experiential and respectful. *Proceedings of the international conference Useful and Critical: the position of research and design*, September 9-11, U.I.A.H.
- Plutchik, R 1962 *The Emotions: Facts, Theories and a new model*. New York: Random House
- Plutchik, R. 2001. The nature of emotions. *American Scientist*. Research Triangle Park. Jul/Aug, Vol. 89 (4): 344-341
- Plutchik, R. 2003. *Emotions an Life - Perspectives from Psychology, Biology, and Evolution*, American Psychological association
- Pollack, R. 2001. *Interior Design Supports the .Knowledge Age*. ASID Future Work 2020
- Propost., R. 1968 *The Office: A facility based on change*. The Business Press.
- Reeves, B & Nass, C. 1996. *The Media Equation*. Cambridge Univ Press, England
- Seligman, M. E. P. 1974. Depression and learned helplessness. In Friedman, R. J, and
- Skoldberg, K. 1994. Tales of change: Public administration reform and narrative mode. *Organization science*, Vol. 5(2): 219-238

Stone, P. J. and Luchetti, R. 1985. Your office is where you are. *Harvard business review*, March-April

Veitch, J. and Gifford, R. 1996. Choice, Perceived Control, and Performance Decrements in the Physical Environment. *Journal of Environmental Psychology* 16, 269-276

Vince, R. and Bourssine, M. 1996. Paradox, defense and attachment; accessing and working with emotions and relations underlying organizational change. *Organization studies*, Vol. 17(1): 1-21

Vischer, J. 1995. Strategic Work-Space Planning. *Sloan Management Review*, Fall: 33- 42.

Walsh, J. P. 1995. Managerial and organizational cognition: notes from a trip down memory lane. *Organization science*, Vol. 6: 280-321

Watson, D. 2000. *Mood and Temperament*. New York: Guilford Press

Wheeler, G. 2001. Work Pattern Emerging in the 21st Century. *ASID Future Work 2020*

Wright, L "Powerful Change." *Burlington Free Press* (VT), 5 October 2003: 1E.
Case Study Draft. *SEI Investments: Redesigning Business*. Corporate Design Foundation and Boston University, 2003.

Wundt, W. 1924. *An introduction to psychology*. London: Allen & Unwin.

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